

Women, Disability, and Inclusion – Scientific Excellence in Bulgaria
GA No. 952369

Deliverable 3.1

Visibility and empowerment guidelines

A roadmap to empower and enhance the visibility of scholars and academic institutions

Work Package:	WP3
Lead Beneficiary:	UNIGE
Authors:	UNIGE, with contributions by the other partners
Due date:	M9
Submission Date:	04-10-2021
Deliverable Type:	Report
Dissemination Level:	Public

Copyright and legal notice

The views expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or position of the European Commission. Neither the authors nor the MILIEU Consortium are responsible for the use which might be made of the information contained here.

Version history

0.1	15/09/2021	Cinzia Leone, Rita Bencivenga	Structure of contents, first draft
0.9	up to 3/10/2021	All the partners	Second draft
1	4/10/2021	Cinzia Leone, Rita Bencivenga	Final revision

Deliverable abstract

The main goal of this deliverable is to enhance the visibility and empower scholars and especially ESRs by guiding them into developing self-promotional skills and expertise for popularizing their research and academic work. The deliverable presents a series of strategies and reference points to help scholars better navigate their way into the international academic world. It provides insight and guides on using scientific social networks, public profiles, scientific databases, networking opportunities presented by associations or academic forums, EU networking and funding resources, grant opportunities and useful productivity applications.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Social Networks and Profiles for Scholars	5
3. Bibliographic Databases and Indexing	7
4. European Union Resources	9
4.1 EU Funding and Grant Opportunities for Researchers	10
5. Academic and Research Associations	12
6. Useful Resources and Networking with Other Projects	14
7. MILIEU Partners' and Related International Conferences	16
8. Apps for Focus and Productivity	17

1. Introduction

The main condition for being part of the academic world, namely - to receive recognition from your fellow scholars, has been recently broadened to a whole new global level with the visibility and research promotion possibilities offered by the latest technologies. With the fast advancing rate of technologization, it is sometimes a challenge for scholars nowadays to stay on top of the various paths and must-have channels for communication and networking. This is especially true for young scholars and ESRs, who are at the beginning of their careers and cannot rely on previous experience and connections.

In this document, we suggest a series of strategies and reference points that can help scholars and especially ESRs to better navigate their way into the international academic world.

As it is impossible to give indications for each discipline and research interest, the document suggests a general path that everyone will adapt to their own situation.

Making one's research path more inclusive - one of the primary purposes of the MILIEU project, is nowadays indispensable, not only for ethical and social justice reasons but also to access EU funding. Therefore, this document includes specific references essential for the incorporation of a gender perspective, respect for diversity, and inclusion in a broad sense in one's professional career.

The document includes references and links active as of September 30, 2021. The world of research is by its nature in constant motion. Therefore, those who read the document later may no longer find some references or discover that some networks have changed. However, we believe that the textual parts that include advice and strategies will allow readers to move on other paths, reaching the main objective of becoming researchers connected and able to interact competently with their research sector and the professional world in a broad sense.

2. Social Networks and Profiles for Scholars

Researchers use social media for various reasons beyond increasing their visibility, including commenting on others' research, discussing research interests, and monitoring their and others' metrics.

Once you have created your profile on one or more of the platforms we recommend, keep it updated and regularly visit social media. It is essential to be very specific when indicating your research field and interests and when searching for connections and collaborations in that field and those particular interests. It is advisable not to waste time following people and interests that are marginal to your professional and research interests.

You may start registering on social networks such as **Academia**, **ResearchGate** and add one or two more specific platforms, once you have detected them.

Academia (<https://www.academia.edu>) is a platform for sharing academic research which allows you to share your published or unpublished papers and follow and promote the work of your colleagues. Regarding the type of access, you can track your mentions and use the analytical tools to gain insight into your profile's visitors.

ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net>) is a professional network for scientists and researchers which allows you to connect with colleagues and share your scientific output and expertise and showcase your past and current research and projects. There are dedicated sections for asking professional questions and starting discussions or for finding job opportunities.

Other possibilities to promote your work are public profiles such as **Google Scholar**, **Publons** or **Scopus** profile.

Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com>) is a web search engine that indexes scholarly literature across various platforms and like Publons is not a social network per se. Registering a profile, however, allows you to monitor and add and organise your publications in order to track mentions and indexes. As profiles are public this is a good way to promote your work.

Publons (<https://publons.com/about/home>) is a platform powered by Web of Science, ORCID, and integrations with thousands of scholarly journals that lets you track your publications, citation metrics, peer reviews and journal editing work.

Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com/home.uri>) as well provides the possibility to register an account and build your profile to promote your work.

We also recommend **Mendeley** (<https://www.mendeley.com>) or **Zotero** (<https://www.zotero.org>), although it is essential to specify that these sites also serve other functions. In fact, beyond being social networking sites, they help catalogue the scientific resources you use for your research work and looking for new ones. They allow you to create in-text citations, footnotes, bibliographies, use the most popular citation styles (APA, MLA,

Chicago), and many other functions. Both are also available as desktop apps on Windows and Mac.

While you can and should upload an updated CV on the previous sites, you cannot avoid registering on **ORCID** (<https://orcid.org>), as it provides a persistent digital identifier (an ORCID iD) that you own and control, and that distinguishes you from every other researcher. On the ORCID website, you will connect your iD with your professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, peer review, to make only a few examples. This unique iD identifier will allow you to share your information with other systems, with numerous advantages such as “ensuring you get recognition for all your contributions, saving you time and hassle, and reducing the risk of errors”. It is especially useful for researchers who publish in different languages/alphabets or if you change your affiliation or even name. Once you have your iD, do not forget to add it to your CV and publications. An ORCID iD is also important as it allows you to save time, as you can register on some platforms using the iD and at least part of the information will be automatically transferred from the ORCID platform. Having your data on ORCID is also useful for applying for European grants and projects, as these might ask for you to include your ORCID ID in the application.

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/feed>) in the past was meant primarily for business connections, professional development, HR and recruiting. Nowadays, researchers and academics may find LinkedIn helpful. LinkedIn for Education (<https://university.linkedin.com>) facilitates connections between students, alumni, schools, and employers. As for any other resource, organisation, social medium, adding "disability", "gender", "diversity" to the name of the resource/organisation, social media in a search on Google will direct you to groups dedicated to these topics, where you can establish valuable exchanges of information.

Elsevier (<https://www.elsevier.com>) is a publishing company, offering useful resources to researchers, such as information on conferences and organising webinars. This is not the only publishing company offering a broad range of activities. Once one understands the website's potential, it will be easier to find other publishing companies, more directly related to specific fields, and explore the possibilities they offer. Attending the webinars, for example, may favour academic contacts with the speakers, collecting references, and remaining updated on the most updated information on numerous topics. Interesting for MILIEU participants could be the webinars available on the website, e.g. Ethics & AI: Gender, Race and Computer Science, and Brain Research: Women in Neuroscience. An entire section is dedicated to Gender & Diversity (<https://www.elsevier.com/connect/topics/gender-and-diversity>). Also, the Elsevier Research Academy provides useful webinars (<https://researcheracademy.elsevier.com>).

3. Bibliographic Databases and Indexing

Getting familiar and understanding the bibliographic databases and indexing is essential for building your publication strategy in a way that will be beneficial for your career and acknowledgement.

It may go without saying but publishing in English, in peer-reviewed and indexed (preferably high-indexed) journals is one of the main prerequisites for visibility and empowerment for both the individual scholars and the institution.

As with all other resources, there are dozens of bibliographic databases, however, two stand out in terms of recognition - Web of Science and Scopus.

The **Web of Science** (<https://clarivate.com/products/web-of-science>) provides subscription-based access to multiple databases that provide citation data for many academic disciplines. It is run by Clarivate Analytics (Thomson Reuters, previously) and currently combines six topical and five regional databases/indexes. Access to the Web of Science is often offered by academic libraries. Based on the two most important databases - the Science Citation Index Expanded and the Social Sciences Citation Index - a yearly publication is made - the Journal Citation Report (JCR) which is also integrated and accessible via WoS. It provides information about academic journals in the natural sciences and social sciences, including impact factors. The WoS citation indexes are considered to be the most accurate, hence the high-ranked journals in WoS - the ones with high JCR impact factor - are the most prestigious ones.

Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com>) is an abstract and citation database run by Elsevier. Scopus covers almost 35 thousand peer-reviewed journals in top-level subject fields: life sciences, social sciences, physical sciences and health sciences. It covers three types of sources: book series, journals, and trade journals. All journals covered in the Scopus database are reviewed for sufficiently high quality each year and are given quality measures such as h-Index, CiteScore, SJR (SCImago Journal Rank) and SNIP (Source Normalized Impact per Paper). At Scopus, you can check ranks without needing an account.

In certain cases, Scopus and Web of Science are wrongly considered to present the same indexing. It has to be clear that the two databases present two *different* indexing systems. Web of Science is given priority in many countries and academic positions, and very often certain journals indexed in Scopus are not indexed in Web of Science.

An example of another index that can be useful is **ERIH Plus** (<https://dbh.nsd.uib.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/>) - The European Reference Index for the Humanities and Social Sciences. It is an index containing bibliographic information on academic journals in the humanities and social sciences and was created with the idea to propose an alternative to the commercial WoS and Scopus. ERIH Plus aims to promote accessibility of scientific works and to expand the visibility of scholars publishing in languages other than

English. To be indexed in ERIH Plus a journal must be of high quality and also provide free access to the articles.

A word of caution is needed with regard to indexing as there are some indexes invented with the sole idea to mimic the trusted ones. They fake impact and prestige trying to attract scientists to publish in predatory journals. So, always check the indexing in the official websites before trusting a journal. Other aspects to check are to verify the existence of a peer-reviewed system and an editorial board. Also, publishing should not require a fee.

Some examples of other databases that do not include indexing but can be useful are:

ScienceDirect (<https://www.sciencedirect.com>) is another bibliographic database of scientific and medical publications hosted by Elsevier which covers journals and books published primarily by them. According to its own account, it hosts over 18 million pieces of content from more than 4,000 academic journals and 30,000 e-books of this publisher.

JSTOR (<https://www.jstor.org>) is another useful database, which is an academic and research English database for all disciplines. According to the official website, **JSTOR** is a database that is part of the ITHAKA non-profit organization alongside Artstone, Ithaka S+R and Portico. JSTOR provides academic information in 75 disciplines using 12 million academic journal articles, books and primary sources. To access this database the user has to sign up with an account or using their institution credentials. However, although the catalogue this webpage offers is very vast, not all the materials are accessible to all institutions.

Dialnet (<https://dialnet.unirioja.es>) is another important tool for researchers regarding databases. Dialnet was created by the informatics service of Universidad la Rioja (Spain) and, right now, according to their official website, is one of the biggest bibliographical portals worldwide. Its main goal is to promote the visibility of Spanish academic and scientific publications. Despite this Spanish-centric approach, the website is available in different languages and there are academic publications available in several languages as well. Dialnet is a database focused on Humanities and Social Sciences that includes articles, chapters from books or congress and conference minutes. In addition, it works as a thesis repository.

CEEOL - Central and Eastern European Online Library (<https://www.cceol.com>) is another useful database focused on academic e-journals and e-books in the Humanities and Social Sciences from and about Central and Eastern Europe. According to the site itself, CEEOL covers more than 2000 journals and 690.000 articles, over 4500 ebooks and 6000 grey literature documents. Some of the publications are free but you need to register.

It is up to you to identify which of these examples, or others, can be valuable in your career, but we generally advise you to use the WoS and Scopus databases in order to be able to identify and subsequently publish in as higher-ranked journals as possible. As usual, the advice is to start registering and using several resources to understand their functioning and select progressively those who can help you in your career. Another useful strategy is to again follow the leading scientist in your specific field and try publishing in the same journals. Your final aim should be to reach an equilibrium between the time spent on databases and the benefits to your work.

4. European Union Resources

The European Union (EU) has numerous research and innovation funding programmes. Therefore you must acquire:

- in-depth knowledge of the programmes more relevant to your discipline;
- a clear understanding of your potential role in a research project;
- competence in adding sex, gender and intersectional perspectives and analyses to your work;
- understanding of the importance of the Gender Equality Plan of the institution you work for (or apply to work for) to be able to interact and collaborate with its activities.

To start acquiring the above competencies and knowledge, you should acquire familiarity with:

The Funding and Tenders Portal of the European Commission (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>), which is the main site and entry point for participants and experts in funding programmes and tenders managed by the European Commission and other EU bodies. On the Funding and Tenders Portal, you can find all the information about funding programmes, open and forthcoming calls, guides, brochures, etc. The Portal is also the place you submit your project proposals and manage your winning projects.

The project partner locator which used to be part of CORDIS is now directly integrated in the Funding and Tenders Portal - as a dedicated section for every call. That is why registering in the Portal also allows you to post a short bio and directly connect to possible partners, thus building your own network of useful contacts and scholars working in your domain of interest.

The CORDIS website (<https://cordis.europa.eu>), where you can find information on all funded proposals, helpful to understand the current state of the art in your field, and examples of proposals, to understand in what an EU project differs from a research project funded by other sources.

The Gendered Innovations website (<https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu>) and its contents, for all what relates to sex, gender and intersectionality.

The **EU website** pages contain information about its vision and mission on topics of interest of MILIEU. The following documents are all part of a Union of Equality (https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/gender_equality_strategy_factsheet_en.pdf) to which the European Commission has committed itself, in order to accelerate the process towards equality, diversity and inclusion in Europe:

- the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020- 2025, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0152&from=EN>
- the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_810
- the LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020-2025 https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/lgbtiq_strategy_2020-2025_en.pdf
- the EU Roma strategic framework for equality, inclusion and participation for 2020-2030 https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu_roma_strategic_framework_for_equality_inclusion_and_participation_for_2020_-_2030_0.pdf

Other sources for your future career are European Union-initiated bodies dedicated exclusively to specific topics. You may start with:

EIGE - the European Institute for Gender Equality, an EU decentralised agency, distinct from the EU institutions, a specialist body set up to advise the Institutions and the Member States in gender equality related topics, and in particular its section on Gender Equality Plans (<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/what-gender-equality-plan-gep>)

EIT - The European Institute of Innovation & Technology (<https://eit.europa.eu>) an independent body of the European Union set up to deliver innovation across Europe. We mention in particular Women@EIT (<https://womeneit.eu>), a community that aims to activate women's power in European innovation and entrepreneurship.

Other EU agencies could be interesting for your work. The list is very long; you may visit the more strictly related links to your scientific interests on the following page: https://europa.eu/european-union/contact/institutions-bodies_en#agencies.

4.1 EU Funding and Grant Opportunities for Researchers

Among all possibilities for funding offered by the EU, grant opportunities are specifically worth mentioning here.

Euraxess (<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu>) is a pan-European initiative backed by the European Union, member states and associated countries, offering a complete range of information and personalised support services, to researchers, innovators, research organisations/universities and businesses. It provides practical support to researchers and their families as they relocate for work. After registering, it is worth dedicating time to explore its various sections, from jobs and funding to career development.

Euraxess offer information also on **Euraxess Worldwide**, offering information on opportunities for European researchers working outside Europe and non-European researchers wishing to come to Europe: ASEAN, CHINA, INDIA, JAPAN, LATIN AMERICA & CARIBBEAN STATES, NORTH AMERICA, KOREA, AUSTRALIA & NEW ZEALAND.

EURAXESS National Portals offer more detailed information at the national level. The four National Portals of the MILIEU partners' countries are <https://www.euraxess.bg>, <https://www.euraxess.it> and <https://www.euraxess.es>.

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) are a set of major research fellowships created by the European Union/European Commission to support research in the European Research Area. As an individual, you may be interested in particular either in applying for an **MSCA Individual Fellowship**, or to join an **MSCA Doctoral Network**, where usually several PhD positions are opened. You may consult the list of funded Networks, to search for the one in your research field. You may find detailed descriptions of past and current research activities in the CORDIS database. This is particularly useful when you start thinking of submitting an application, as it will allow you to position your research interest among proposals in the same field, as well as using their results for planning your activities.

The **European Research Council (ERC)** is a public body for funding scientific and technological research conducted within the European Union. Exploring the website is useful for many reasons, even if you are not submitting a proposal. Interviews, information on research topics, and events can offer you hints and ideas. It is worth exploring, in particular, a workshop titled: "SEX AND GENDER DIMENSION IN FRONTIER RESEARCH", to see how these dimensions can be applied in concrete research projects (<https://erc.europa.eu/event/sex-and-gender-dimension-frontier-research>).

5. Academic and Research Associations

It is always interesting and useful for researchers to know who is active at the international level in their field and associations and networks are designed for this purpose among others. Being active in an association or network allows you to stay ahead of the-state-of-art and also to participate in conferences, seminars, working groups and become part of the international discourse on a topic.

As there are numerous groups organised in networks, associations, interest groups, and the like for any research field, it is crucial to understand which are more valuable. Generally, knowing the most distinguished scholars in an area helps identify the best associations, as those are the ones to which the top scholars belong. This information is often available on the scholars' CVs, the Association's Annual report, or the Association website.

It takes time sometimes to identify the most active groups; therefore, as already mentioned in previous sections, in the beginning, careful observation of a wider pool of possibilities will allow later on to focus better.

Another possible strategy is to join big professional associations such as e.g. the **International Sociological Association** (<https://www.isa-sociology.org/>); the **European Sociological Association** (<https://www.europeansociology.org>); the **International Association of Women Philosophers** (<http://www.women-philosophy.org>), the **International Federation of Philosophical Societies** (<https://www.fisp.org>). The **Bulgarian Sociological Association** (<http://bsa-bg.eu>) is a collective member of both ISA and ESA, so becoming a member of this national body is also worth considering. Doing so allows you to follow several of the different research committees or work/thematic groups that are close to your field of interest. Specifically for young scholars, there are opportunities to receive sponsored memberships or grants for conferences in both of the above associations.

With regard to MILIEU core teams we have selected a small number of associations as an example for such that are worth monitoring:

- the **European Association for Gender Research, Education and Documentation - ATGender**, (<https://atgender.eu>), a broad association for academics, practitioners, activists and institutions in the field of Women's and Gender Studies, Feminist Research, women's rights, gender equality and diversity.
- **UNESCO's UNITWIN Network on Gender, Media and ICTs** (<https://en.unesco.org/gamagandunitwin>) a worldwide network of universities established to promote an integrated system of research, education and dissemination activities on these topics across all world regions
- The **Section Gender, Sexuality and Communication of the European Communication Research and Education Association - ECREA** (<https://ecrea.eu/Gender-and-Communication>), that aims to bring together scholars who approach issues within the field of communication with a specific interest in gender. Gender is conceptualized in a broad sense.

- The mission of the **Gender and Communication Section of the International Association for Media and Communication Research - IAMCR** (<https://iamcr.org/s-wg/section/gen>) is to foster and encourage all knowledge, scholarship, empirical work and theoretical debates in the field of gender and its relation to media and communications.
- **The LGBTQ and Sexuality Section of the Association for Slavic, East European, & Eurasian Studies** (<https://www.aseees.org>) which was created to promote all forms of LGBTQ studies in Slavic, East European, and Eurasian societies, including but not limited to history, literary and cultural studies, social sciences, and interdisciplinary studies.
- **The Gender and Politics Section of the European Consortium for Political Research -** (<https://ecpr.eu>) forms a broad-based network on issues relating to the study of gender and sexuality in politics and world politics. The Group actively encourages workshops, panels and research groups with an emphasis on gender and seeks to increase the profile of women in the main fields of political science.

6. Useful Resources and Networking with Other Projects

Some projects and collaborative networks have produced manuals and guidelines that provide useful information in what concerns gender, disability and inclusion studies. Also, links to RRI projects are included. A selection of the resources is offered below:

- **AGEMI** — Advancing Gender Equality in Media Industries:
 - [A Resources Bank of Good Practices.](#)
- **EIGE** — European Institute for Gender Equality (includes a huge amount of tools and links to other projects, just a few are shown below):
 - [EIGE's Gender Equality Training toolkit](#)
 - [Gender-sensitive communication | EIGE](#)
 - [European Union | 2020 | Gender Equality Index](#)
- **GARCIA** — Gendering the academy and research: combating career instability and asymmetries:
 - [Selection of measures for integrating gender into research and curricula in six European countries](#)
 - [Toolkit for Integrating Gender Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching](#)
 - [Supporting Early Career Researchers through Gender Action Plans. A Design and Methodological Toolkit](#)
- **GEARING ROLES** — Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to transform Gender ROLES:
 - [Outputs](#) (videos and podcasts)
- **GENDER-NET**:
 - [Elevating promising practice: Potential transnational actions for integrating gender analysis into research,](#)
 - [Manuals with guidelines on the integration of sex and gender analysis into research contents](#)
 - [Recommendations for curricula development and indicators](#)
- **GENERA** — Gender equality network in the European research area:
 - [GENERA Toolbox for tailored Gender Equality Plans](#)
- **LIBRA** — Leading innovative measures to reach gender balance in research activities:
 - [LIBRA Recruitment Handbook - 2nd edition](#)
- **TRIGGER** — Transforming institutions by gendering contents and gaining equality in research:
 - [Deliverable D2.7 Toolbox for gender diversity management](#)
- **FoTRRIS**. *How to co-create RRI projects.*
 - Available at <http://fotrris-h2020.eu/tag/cookbook/>
- **RAISD**. Capacity building courses for researchers.
 - [Capacity Building](#)
- **Sage online course**: Creating a gender-sensitive university.

- https://www.tcd.ie/tcgel/international-projects/SAGE/creating_a_gender_sensitive_institution/index.php This course, in three modules, has been developed to provide valuable knowledge for those in higher education who wish to advance gender equality in their workplace and to address gender imbalances in academia and research. We recommend the third session, [The Gender Dimension in Research](#), as it can be useful in learning how to embed gender in your research activities and projects.

7. MILIEU Partners' and Related International Conferences

Participating in conferences is a powerful strategy to create professional networks and job opportunities. It is impossible to provide an exhaustive list, that in any case would be outdated in a few months. We invite you to constantly monitor new conferences in your field, reading the programmes and proceedings of the old ones, and try to participate in the most relevant ones.

With regard to MILIEU and its core topics we recommend exploring the following forthcoming conferences that are scheduled for 2021-2022:

- I International Conference on Communication and Disability (October 28-29, 2021), Madrid. <https://congreso.proyectocompensa.es/>
- VIII Creative Cities Conference (December 1-2, 2021) <https://congresociudadescreativas.es/>
- Learning, Technology and Digital Skills in Education (November 25-26, 2021) <https://congresoinnovaciondocente.es>
- The Future of Childhood is Now. The 9th International Conference on Child and Teen Consumption (May 4-6, 2022). Deadline: 24/10/2021. Please notice **ESRs and academic staff from partner organizations are invited** to be part of the academic board
- Council for European Studies/Gender and sexuality network - June 2022, Lisbon. <https://councilforeuropeanstudies.org/lisbon-call-for-proposals/>
- The 6th European Geographies of Sexualities Conference - planned to be held on-site in Cádiz, Spain, 14-16 September 2022 <https://2022.egsconference.com/>
- Talking bodies--disability and gender. Postponed for 2022 <https://www1.chester.ac.uk/institute-gender-studies/talking-bodies-2021-conference>
- Women in Management. Experiences from Central and Eastern European Countries. 9-10 December 2021, Warsaw, Poland. <https://www.kozminski.edu.pl/en/women-management-experiences-central-and-eastern-european-countries>
- The European Seating Symposium. Postponed for 2022. To take place in Dublin, 14-17 June 2022 <https://www.europeanseatingsymposium.eu/>
- GeDiMIRT (Gender Dimension in Physics and Math-Intensive Research and Teaching) Postponed for 2022. To take place June 22/23, 2022 in Lund University <https://indico.desy.de/event/29452/>

8. Apps for Focus and Productivity

Alongside databases and social connections with other peers, or support from institutions and associations, practical tricks for successfully focusing on scientific work are essential for the productivity and thus scientific production of scholars. As easy as it may seem, this is an extremely difficult task with the continual electronic stimulus that we receive from the internet, the media, or social network apps, either scientific or not. In order to control and redirect productivity the following apps and webpages are useful:

SelfCare is an app that allows the user to block different web pages (Twitter or YouTube for example) by adding them to a Black List during a set time selected by the user. Once the time is selected and the block is on, the user will not be receiving notifications from those pages and if he or she tries to check on said pages they will be blocked. This app is available for IOS and Android on computers and other devices such as phones completely for free. Another good alternative is **ColdTurkey**.

In terms of productivity, a relevant app for all kinds of researchers and students is **BeFocused**. BeFocused helps the researcher to organize their tasks following the Pomodoro technique (arranging tasks a set of intervals and after completing said time allowing you short breaks and, once you have completed said interval of time, the app reminds him or her to take a longer break). Example: The task is writing the methodological chapter of the research and the researcher decides to set a timer for 1 hour and an interval of two hours (that in those two hours total the methodology has to be done). This set of times will remind the researcher that after the first hour of work (which is the short interval) it is time for a short break of ten minutes. After completing the two hours the task would be completed and, therefore, the device will remind him or her to take a longer break.

Regarding attention and focussing, a very useful resource is the website **A Soft Murmur**. This webpage allows the researcher to stay focused when the environment surrounding him or her is very noisy. The web page allows the person to select which kind of noises he or she wants to listen to while working: from pure white noise to natural sounds such as bonfire, rain or waves, to complete environmental sounds like coffee shops ambience. The level of the sound can be regulated and mixed with others. A Soft Murmur does not need a user and a password to be used and it is completely free, and it is also available as an app for other electronic devices like mobile phones.